

Impact of Linguistics in Mathematical Learning

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ABSTRACT : Language and linguistics are considered to be part of a social activity. A very challenging view of a biocentric language may become the backbone for the development of an ecologically sensitive lexicon and grammar in education, be it primary, secondary, or tertiary. As a powerful cognitive resource, language is responsive to the intellectual and social needs of a community. Students learn not only the language of their home communities but also specific varieties of that language appropriate to various social settings. Students' linguistic abilities play an important role in their mathematical learning and conceptual processing. Achievement in mathematics is influenced by the student's proficiency in the language of instruction. Mathematical language has its own vocabulary, syntax, semantic and discourse properties. Ecology of language plays a significant role in mathematical learning. In this paper an attempt has been made to find this role.

Keywords : Linguistics, ecology, language, mathematical language, learning.

Introduction

Research in mathematics education, language acquisition, cognitive learning, and general pedagogy highlights the importance of collaborative learning and teaching to achieve student success (Vygotsky, 1978; Schoenfield, 1992). Further, learning processes in mathematics and foreign languages are alike, in the sense that context, total immersion, and cognitive learning play a significant role in comprehension, thus knowledge retention. Accordingly, the belief that students need to understand mathematics in context and to apply

complex concepts to meaningful real world situations is based on that preliminary premise. Mathematics educators have been aware that many processes associated with student learning, the development of critical thinking, discovery learning, and student engagement in “doing” mathematics are facilitated when mathematics is integrated across different areas of the curriculum (NCTM, 1989).

Learning school subjects in a language that is not the students' first language (L1) has become a reality in many parts of the world due to sociopolitical reasons, advances in technology

and better and faster communication systems. Understanding the psychological dimensions of bilingualism within the context of the classroom is crucial for educational policy makers who make decisions about curriculum development, instructional practices, and student evaluation. From a cognitive perspective, examining the processes of comprehension and understanding of academic subjects learned in a second language (L2) is pivotal to addressing issues of learning and instruction. The impact of bilingual education on the teaching and learning process is complex, especially since one goal is to make the process of teaching and learning in a second language as natural as in one's first language, without compromising the knowledge, competence and performance of either language.

Ecology of Language

It is well to remember that each metaphor is only a partial construction of reality and secondly that each one construes and communicates, often implicitly, modes of thought and worldviews about the relationship, which affect both personal behavior and societal arrangements. Thus, what is needed is (1) an awareness of metaphors as linguistic devices that construe and communicate the complex reality of the relationship in a partial and biased way; (2) a critical approach to comprehending discourse that uses such metaphors as linguistic devices; (3) a mindfulness of how/when we use them in discourse.

Vygotsky's belief that human development - child development as well as the development of all *humankind* - is the result of interactions between people and their social environment. These interactions are not limited to actual people but also involve cultural artifacts, mainly

language-based (written languages, number systems, various signs, and symbols). Many of these cultural artifacts serve a dual purpose: not only do they make possible the integration of a growing child into the culture but they also transform the very way the child's mind is being formed. Of all the processes involved in acquisition of mental tools, Vygotsky focused primarily on the use of language. For him, language is both the most important mental tool and a medium facilitating the acquisition of other mental tools.

There is a need for an ergative language where language expresses Earth as an active subject rather than a passive object that is acted upon. Capitalizing the term Nature and using the personal pronoun of "she" or possessive noun "her" for Earth are other examples of such language change. Particularly, Swimme and Berry present some of the most innovative and profound suggestions for an Earth-centered language. They, first of all, suggest the new metaphor *Nature as celebration*, based upon modern experience of Nature in which the universe is considered "as a single, multiform, sequential, celebratory event". The human role in this celebratory event is "to enable this entire community to reflect on and to celebrate itself and its deepest mystery in a special mode of conscious self-awareness.". They also point to the need for an Ecozoic dictionary. They argue that since substantive words, such as society, freedom, justice, literacy, progress, etc. are undergoing transformation, their meanings need to be extended to include the various members of the Earth community. They think that the greatest linguistic change that has to take place is the change "from present efforts at an exclusively univocal, literal, scientific, objective language to a multivalent language much richer

in its symbolic and poetic qualities.” Such shift would re-enchant the impoverished Western languages. They point to the languages of primal cultures as a source of such new symbolism using their myths and metaphors to embroider the basic Universe story that science has been able to tell. Finally, they emphasize the importance of story as a linguistic device.

The main challenge is to compose an integral and complete story of the *great liturgy of the universe* that would function as “the comprehensive context of our human understanding of ourselves.” That task not only requires imaginative power and intellectual understanding, but also a return to the mythic origins of the scientific venture. Thus a very challenging view of a biocentric language may become the backbone for the development of an ecologically sensitive lexicon and grammar in education, be it primary, secondary, or tertiary.

Ecology and Linguistics

Language and linguistics are considered to be part of a social activity constituted by and constituting a social praxis, and therefore part of a meaningful and value-based process. Linguistics is social activities that either confirm or criticise social praxis. Therefore, any change of our use of language is at the same time a change of the social praxis. Social praxis is constituted by some core contradictions that both constrain and condition every social activity including language use and linguistics. Any phenomenon in our social praxis is dialectically determined by a conjuncture of all the core contradictions although one being dominant. One of the core contradictions is “culture-nature” and in our time it is part of an ecological crisis. The ecological crisis co-determines the place and function of language and linguistics.

There are as many as 60 percent of all languages are already endangered, and go far as to claim that some of the endangered languages have much to tell us about the natural world, e.g., invaluable information about ecological matters. Language disappearance is an erosion or extinction of ideas, of ways of knowing and ways of talking about the world and human experience.

Language and culture are of a piece, in that language is a cultural resource and creation that reflects culture’s values, experience and goals and is used to transit them across generations. As Nieto(1999) says, “The language, language variety or dialect one speaks is culture made manifest”. Perhaps the most powerful language differences lie at the intersection of language and culture. They have to do with the sociocultural aspects of language use—how children and adults are expected to participate in conversation, argument, discussion, story telling, explanation or recounting of experience (Gee,1996; Heath,1983). In a society where people keep a lot of pets of different kinds, there is likely to be a considerable variety of names and forms of address used depending on the kind of pet, e.g., horse, cat, and the circumstances , e.g., whether you are alone with the pet or in a public view, feeding it, or reprimanding it.

As a powerful cognitive resource, language is responsive to the intellectual and social needs of a community. Students learn not only the language of their home communities but also specific varieties of that language appropriate to various social settings. The forms of language that children learn are the uses of language modeled in their home communities and the ways people in various role groups are expected to use language.

Linguistics in Sustainable Mathematical Learning

It is widely accepted that students' linguistic abilities play an important role in their learning and conceptual processing of academic subjects. This role is particularly important in the domain of mathematics, where students have to use their linguistic abilities before conceptualizing a problem in mathematical terms, so that they can arrive at a correct numerical representation and problem solution. In this sense, achievement in mathematics is influenced by the student's proficiency in the language of instruction. Miura (2001) argued that students' mathematics understanding is influenced by the cultural factors that shape the representations that are found within the classroom. These factors include the characteristics of the language of instruction, and the characteristics of the mathematical terms that are specific to that language. The representations are of two types: instructional, which refer to classroom discourse, (i.e., students teacher exchanges and the language of instruction) and cognitive, which refer to the individual student's representations.

Any mathematics curriculum includes four basic areas, namely concepts, computation, applications, and problem solving. Mathematical concept formation is a complex process that involves perceiving the underlying relationships between mathematical ideas (Reed, 1984). To achieve this, the student must have the ability to translate from the verbal formulation to the underlying mathematical relationship. Then, the student must also have the ability to construct the mathematical conceptual representation on which the problem solving process will operate. During these activities, students may encounter

difficulty in understanding the language of the teacher and or the text.

Mathematical language has its own vocabulary, syntax, semantic and discourse properties. In terms of vocabulary, mathematics includes words that are specific to the domain (e.g., coefficient, denominator, etc.), and day to day words that take on a specific meaning within the context of mathematics (e.g., equal, rational, table, column, etc.). Competence in this specific vocabulary is crucial to students' mathematical understanding especially as they progress to higher grades. It means that they have to learn that the terms are related to the context in which they occur. Additionally, students have to learn another vocabulary that includes the extensive system of mathematical symbols, which have their own meaning within the mathematical context. These symbols increase in conceptual density as students move up in the curriculum. Students must also understand that there is a lack of a one to one correspondence between mathematical symbols and the words they represent, and the role of logical connectors (e.g., if...then, if and only if, but, etc.) which indicate the nature of the relationship between parts of the text.

Learning to communicate verbally and in writing about mathematics is important. This can be emphasized in the classroom by addressing correct use of vocabulary and grammar, encouraging the use of both written and spoken mathematical language, assisting with the translation of phrases or sentences to mathematical language and, in general, encouraging students to discuss mathematics (Oldfield, 1996). Friedlander and Tabach (2001) believe that verbal reasoning can be useful in solving problems, although its use in the

classroom has not been fully legitimized. However, they also caution that, despite allowing students to make the connection of mathematics with other domains and everyday life, verbal representation can also interfere with mathematics communication given its ambiguous, distracting, and misleading nature, its lack of universality and its reliance on personal style.

In mathematical talk we use numbers as objects, that is, as nouns. In some languages numbers have a noun morphology. In English, multiplication can be expressed as, say: ‘three times four’ or ‘four times three’ where the three and four can be interchanged without altering the word forms, the grammar or the sense. In other words commutativity is a part of the language of multiplication in English. The point being made is that, within each language, there are particular ways of expressing ideas of quantity, relationships, or space. Although it is possible to describe all these linguistic expressions in each language, there remains a question mark over whether the full complexity of the expression can be rendered in another language.

There are some relationships between memory load of linguistic artifacts and mathematical performance. Consider the number syllables of number words. Chinese words are monosyllabic ; for example, the number 9 is read as *jiu* in Chinese which is one syllable and *sembilan* in Malay which is 3 syllable. The mean number of syllables for the number words from 0 to 10 in Malay is 2.1 compared to 1 in Chinese. Hoosain (1997) cited studies showing that adults speaking Chinese have a digit span of 9.2, whereas that for English

is 7.21. The more the number of syllables the longer it takes to recite the number and more difficult to keep it in short term memory. This becomes even more striking when pupils learn the multiplication tables. The monosyllabic property of the Chinese language may partly explain why pupils in Chinese schools seem to master the multiplication table faster than pupils from other schools. Mastery of the multiplication tables is obviously essential for efficient mental work.

Conclusion

To sustain the mathematical learning students must be equipped with the linguistic skills that allow them to learn to understand the highly specialized and contextualized language of mathematics. Students have to learn vocabulary that includes the extensive system of mathematical symbols, which have their own meaning within the mathematical context as well as ecological context.

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